

Profile Integral, a robust and unified metric for measuring profile concavity

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Abstract— To measure the shape of topographic profiles in two dimensions (height v. distance), we propose a new metric (and develop its related toolbox) based on integrating the area under the profile. It is applicable to any cross-valley profile, slope profile, long profile or arbitrary profile. By analogy with the Hypsometric Integral, we term the metric the Profile Integral. It is a normalized value between 0 and 1 with the value of 0.5 representing either a straight-line long profile or a V-shaped cross-profile and values of > 0.5 for convex profiles and < 0.5 for concave profiles. Correlations with the V-index, the VWDR, the K-curve, the power curve and the quadratic polynomial are analyzed. The advantages of the Profile Integral are (1) its flexibility in providing a metric with similar interpretations for long profiles, slope profiles and valley cross-profiles and (2) its applicability to asymmetric cross-profiles in full, including those close to the confluence of tributary valleys (asymmetric cross-profiles, reaching different heights on each side, are common yet are excluded from most analyses of valleys and troughs). Our toolbox generates smoothed streamlines (thalwegs) to provide starting points for a series of cross-profiles. Applications to glaciated valleys in the Tian Shan (Daxi) and northern Iceland (Eyjafjardardalur) are illustrated.

I. INTRODUCTION

Measures of concavity are used, for example, to characterize slope profiles and river long profiles, to express the degree of cirque development (Çilgin et al., 2024^[1]) and the degree of glacial modification of valleys from V to U-shaped cross-profiles (Harbor, 1995^[2]; Harbor and Wheeler, 1996^[3]). Methods include fitting exponential, power and quadratic functions, and indices

based on width and depth. It is not clear which methods provide the most valuable results.

Here we propose a new metric, the Profile Integral (PI), and develop its related toolbox based on integrating the area under the profile. We then compare it with a range of indices of concavity measures fitted to two-sided valley cross-profiles and to one-sided long or slope profiles. We present correlations between the various indices and exponents and find that our proposed metric, PI, with a simple expression has numerous advantages as a single-index measure of concavity. We advocate its use for a broad range of profiles.

II. PREVIOUS INDICES

Indices applicable to two-sided valley cross-profiles have included: the coefficients ‘a’ and ‘b’ of a power law function to the relationship between the width/depth ratios at different depths of the valley - the VWDR (Valley Width-Depth Ratio) model (Li et al., 2001a^[4]);

$$y = ax^b \quad (1);$$

‘c’ in the quadratic equation

$$y = a + bx + cx^2 \quad (2)$$

(James, 1996^[5]; Li et al., 2001a^[6]); and the

$$\text{V-index} = (Ax/Av) - 1 \quad (3)$$

(Zimmer and Gabet, 2018^[7]), where Ax is the valley cross-sectional area above the profile, up to a fixed height, and Av is the V-shaped area with the same height and width. Finally, as the difference in height on the two sides of a valley is of some importance, the degree of deviation from equality in height can be expressed as:

$$\text{HHratio} = h_{\text{min}}/h_{\text{max}} \quad (4),$$

where h_{min} and h_{max} relate to the heights of left and right valley sides, h_l and h_r in Fig.1c.

Indices for one-sided (slope or long) profiles include ‘a’ and ‘b’ for the power law fit to altitude values, as in equation (1) (there are complications in applying it to a full cross-profile, Harbor and Wheeler, 1992^[3]); ‘a’ and ‘b’ of the exponential fit

$$y = ae^{bx} \quad (5);$$

the coefficient ‘c’ of Kcurve (Krause et al., 2022^[8]):

$$y = (1-x)e^{cx} \quad (6);$$

Profile Closure, the difference between maximum and minimum slope gradient along an axial profile (Li et al., 2024^[9]; cf. Evans and Cox, 1995^[10]); and the Stream length – Gradient index for river long profiles,

$$SL = dH/dL * L \quad (7),$$

where L is the cumulative length from the start point of the stream profile; dH and dL are the differences respectively in elevation and length of a short segment along the stream profile.

III. PROFILE INTEGRAL AND SAMPLING

The newly proposed Profile Integral (PI) is defined as:

$$PI = h_{mean}/H = (E_{mean} - E_{min})/(E_{max} - E_{min}) \quad (8),$$

where h_{mean} is the average of the heights along the profile, H is the height/depth of the profile, E_{mean} , E_{min} , and E_{max} are the average, minimum, and maximum elevations above sea level of all equally spaced points along the profile. PI represents the ratio of the area under the profile to the area ($L * H$) of the profile’s rectangular envelope, or the area under the standardized topography profile if both y (height) and x (width or length) are standardized to [0, 1], which is similar to the

Figure 1. Definition of the profile integral (PI) for a one-sided topographic profile (a), a two-sided valley cross-sectional profile with the same height at both sides (b), and a two-sided asymmetric valley cross-sectional profile with different heights at either side (c): l = left and r = right. (d) extends the definition of the V-index proposed by Zimmer and Gabet (2018), to apply more generally to a two-sided valley cross-sectional profile which is asymmetric, with different heights on the two sides. Av is the triangle area of the two end points and the lowest point of the profile. Ax is the area above the topographic profile, up to the top line of Av.

definition of the hypsometric integral (HI). Fig 1 illustrates its application in different situations, and how the definition of V-index can be adapted to the general situation of each valley side having a different height.

We develop a GIS toolbox to delineate the streamlines (thalwegs), generate cross-sectional profiles along streamlines, and derive PI and other related metrics for both two-sided cross-sectional profiles and one-sided profiles, like stream long profiles. We demonstrate how to use this toolbox for topographic profile analysis in two test areas: one in the Daxi Valley area, eastern Tian Shan, China, and the other in the Eyjafjardardalur area, Northern Iceland. Fig. 2 shows how valley cross-profiles can be defined automatically, starting from the streamline (thalweg) network. Some profile lines are deleted manually because bends in a streamline produced obliquity to the valley-side.

Figure 2. Cross sections in the Daxi Valley area (Tian Shan) generated along the streamlines after excluding those intersecting RGI7 glaciers. The extent of each cross-section is constrained by the lowest (above threshold) convex point on each side of the cross-section. (b) Selected cross sections after visual checks and revisions for valley morphological analysis in the Daxi Valley area. (c) Cross-sections in the Eyjafjardardalur area (Iceland) generated along the streamlines after excluding the cross sections intersecting RGI7 glaciers. (d) 484 cross-sections selected for further analysis after visual checks and revisions based on valley morphological analysis in the Eyjafjardardalur area.

IV. RESULTS

Table I shows strong correlation between PI and the V-index in the Daxi valley area. They both correlate moderately with ‘m’ and ‘n’ coefficients of VWDR, which correlate strongly with each other.

TABLE I. PEARSON CORRELATIONS OF CONCAVITY METRICS IN THE DAXI VALLEY AREA FOR CROSS-PROFILES, n = 123.

	PI	Ln(V_index+1)	Ln(Quad_c)	Ln(VWDR_m)	VWDR_n
PI	1.00				
Ln(V_index+1)	-0.88	1.00			
Ln(Quad_c)	-0.04	-0.18	1.00		
Ln(VWDR_m)	-0.59	0.40	0.03	1.00	
VWDR_n	0.49	-0.27	-0.27	-0.95	1.00

Fig. 3 shows the greater concavity (lower PI) of the trunk glacial trough in the Eyjafjardardalur area (heading north toward Akureyri) compared with tributary troughs. Only a few cross-profiles, mainly near headwaters in the east, show net-convex valley-sides (red). While the frequency distribution of PI values is close to symmetrical, some other indices are highly skewed (Csillik et al., 2015^[11]). Thus, to calculate correlation coefficients, a logarithmic scale is needed for both the quadratic ‘c’ and the VWDR ‘m’ coefficient; and the logarithm of V-index is taken after adding 1 to avoid negative values.

Figure 3. Profile Integrals for glacial troughs in Eyjafjardardalur, northern Iceland.

Table II gives correlations both for the whole set of cross-profiles and (in brackets) for the subset with asymmetry limited to HHratio > 0.7, in the Eyjafjardardalur area. The latter mainly

provides slightly stronger correlations, especially for V-index, because the V-index is a special case of PI for valleys with two sides of equal height, while its calculation for asymmetric cross-profiles differs, as illustrated in Fig. 1 (c) and (d). All correlations for Quad_c are weak for Daxi, but higher for Eyjafjardardalur.

TABLE II. PEARSON CORRELATIONS OF CONCAVITY METRICS IN EYJAFJARÐARDALUR AREA FOR CROSS-PROFILES

	PI	Ln(V_index+1)	Ln(Quad_c)	Ln(VWDR_m)
PI	1.00			
Ln(V_index+1)	-0.85 (-0.99)	1.00		
Ln(Quad_c)	0.65 (0.67)	-0.60 (-0.67)	1.00	
Ln(VWDR_m)	-0.88 (-0.88)	0.78 (0.88)	-0.71 (-0.69)	1.00
VWDR_n	0.76 (0.78)	-0.66 (-0.77)	0.38 (0.37)	-0.91 (-0.92)

The values outside of () are for the whole dataset (n = 747); inside of () are for cross sections with HHratio > 0.70 (n = 446).

Table III gives indices for the 1490 valley-sides with profiles over 100 m long in the Eyjafjardardalur area. Kcurve_c was formulated explicitly to express concavity of cirque profiles (Krause et al., 2022^[8]): its very strong correlation (0.97) with PI shows that both are good indicators of concavity. Although the exponent ‘b’ of the power fit has been used widely to indicate the degree of glacial erosion giving U-shaped valleys, its correlation with PI is only -0.51, whereas that of power exponent ‘a’ is stronger (0.67). It seems that both a and b are required for a power fit to express concavity. The logarithms of both the coefficients of exponential fits have stronger correlations with PI and with Kcurve_c, but ‘a’ has stronger correlations than ‘b’. The stream length - gradient index, SL, has weak correlations, the strongest being only -0.36 with PI.

TABLE III. PEARSON CORRELATIONS FOR HALF-VALLEY METRICS IN EYJAFJARÐARDALUR AREA.

	PI	Closure	Kcurve_c	SL	(Pow_a)	Ln(Pow_b)	Ln(Exp_a)
PI	1.00						
Closure	-0.25	1.00					
Kcurve_c	0.97	-0.27	1.00				
SL	-0.36	0.33	-0.37	1.00			
Pow_a)	0.67	0.13	0.65	-0.15	1.00		
Ln(Pow_b)	-0.51	0.34	-0.45	0.24	0.19	1.00	
Ln(Exp_a)	0.77	-0.20	0.68	-0.31	0.28	-0.87	1.00
Ln(Exp_b)	-0.69	0.25	-0.62	0.34	-0.11	0.94	-0.97

N = 1490. Values >|0.5| are in bold.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We conclude that PI is a robust and flexible descriptor of the overall convexity or concavity of any profile. It is applicable to long profiles, transects and valley cross-profiles including those for valleys with one side higher than the other. It is closely related to the V-index (which can be regarded as a special case of PI) and to Kcurve_c, and is well correlated with VWDR at least for symmetrical valleys. The quadratic 'c' has moderate correlations with PI.

For one-sided profiles, both Profile Closure and Stream Length-Gradient have weak correlations with the other indices, presumably because neither fits the whole profile. There is no space here, however, to illustrate application to river long profiles. Coefficients of exponential and power fits are only moderately correlated with PI because two-parameter models are not good at providing a single index for concavity. Logarithms of 'b' of the power fit and of 'a' and 'b' of the exponential fit, correlate strongly ($r > |0.85|$) with each other.

Our toolbox provides the option of saving all profiles to a folder for detailed analysis of their validity, their particular features and the reasons for variations between indices.

We advocate PI as the preferred index for measuring convexity or concavity of any topographic profiles, including cross-valley, slope, stream long profiles.

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